

TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF ELECTRICITY SUPPLY ON THE BASIS OF INTERACTIVE METHODS

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Annotation: The article examines the specifics of teaching the science of power supply based on interactive methods.

Key words: interactive, method, power source, educational process.

In the new version of the Law "On Education" in the conditions of building a new Uzbekistan, a democratic state and civil society, equipped with high moral and ethical potential, modern professional skills, creative and social activism, logical thinking and the ability to find rational solutions to problems in life. The socio-pedagogical idea was put forward to train a new generation of specialists who will be able to fairly assess their responsibilities, as well as to bring up personnel who are consciously perfecting all-round, educational and professional programs and have a deep sense of responsibility. In the current conditions of socio-economic development and the new construction of spiritual and political life, a person can not grow up as a fully developed, perfect person, if he can not think freely, logically, creatively, if democratic principles are not celebrated, if the personal interests of any age are not protected by law. Therefore, the protection of his rights and freedoms from the social point of view, strengthening his socio-economic and spiritual-political readiness, logical, creative observation while studying in higher education, the development of thinking skills have become one of the important guidelines of state programs.

In this regard, the research work on the formation of creative and logical thinking skills, updating and enrichment of forms and methods of education in the

future staff of higher education institutions is of great importance. In particular, the broad interpretation of the use of interactive teaching methods in the teaching of special subjects is of great pedagogical importance today and is reflected in the following:

1. The need to use interactive teaching methods in the teaching of special subjects.
2. Scientific basis for the use of interactive teaching methods in the teaching of special subjects.
3. Increased need for training creative thinking, creative, entrepreneurial, professional personnel through the introduction of interactive teaching methods in higher education.

Interactive teaching methods and technologies play a special role in the structure of person-centered learning technologies.

Interactive education is one of the most effective forms of developing professional knowledge, skills and competencies in future professionals, in which the independence of the individual is ensured and developed, which is an important factor in the development of creative abilities in students.

Researchers LN Vavilova and TS Banina evaluate the effectiveness of interactive learning as follows:

1. Interactive education allows students to activate cognitive processes, apply the acquired knowledge and skills in real situations, realize their potential, creative research.
2. Interactive teaching methods and technologies - develops motivation in learners, the ability to make the right decisions in non-standard situations, research activity, creative thinking skills.
3. An interactive learning environment creates favorable conditions for learners to see problems, analyze, form an active life position, tolerance, respect for the opinions of others, teamwork, the development of life values.

The issue of activating the learning activities of students has been studied by different authors at different times and is scientifically based. The issues of changing

the form, methods and means of teaching, adapting them to the individual characteristics of the student, the creation of special psychological and didactic conditions of education are studied separately.

When analyzing research related to the theory of education and the development of personality cognitive activity, it can be seen that there are a number of models of teaching in pedagogy today. Including:

1. Passive teacher model - within this model, learners are seen as the object of the learning process. In doing so, students listen to and see learning information.
2. Active learning model - in this process, students act as the object of the teaching process. They are engaged in a wide range of independent work, creative tasks in the process of learning information.
3. Interactive learning model - this learning process is based on regular, active interaction and interaction of learners. In this process, the student and the professor are the awake subjects of the educational process.

In interactive teaching, the teacher is the active organizer of the learning activity, and the student is manifested as the subject of this activity.

In the process of interactive learning, students interact with the physical, social, and educational content being studied. All three of these activity manifestations participate in the learning process in a variety of forms. Including:

physical - change students 'jobs, other

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